

Table 2. Comparison of some physiological traits of Yayou and Shanyou 63. Nanjing, China, 1989.

Trait	Yayou 2	Shanyou 63 (check)	Compared with check ^a
Maximum leaf area index	8.2	7.1	+15.5%
Maximum photosynthetic rate (µmol CO ₂ /m per s)	24.0	20.9	+14.8%*
Specific leaf weight in heading (mg/cm ²)	4.6	3.8	+21.1%*
Chlorophyll content in heading (%)	4.9	4.0	+22.5%*
Relative growth rate (g/kg per d)	40.9	37.8	+8.2%
Net assimilation rate (g/m ² per d)	9.6	6.4	+50.0%
Period leaf activity (d)	73	54	+35.2%*

^a* = significant difference at the 5% level.

area index (LAI) and leaf area duration (LAD) caused a high crop growth rate in the hybrids, leading to the higher average biomass than that of the parents. There was no heterosis in harvest index.

The grain yield potential increased to 11.1-12.5 t/ha, which was much higher than that for the indica or japonica lines. Seed set, however, was low and unstable compared with that of the parents, although the *S-5ⁿ* gene was used. High and stable seed set should therefore be the main objective for cultivating and breeding indica-japonica hybrids.

An example of an indica-japonica hybrid rice is Yayou 2. It was developed by using a chemical hybridizing agent and by crossing indica line 3037 and japonica wide compatibility variety 02428. We compared some of its traits with check Shanyou 63, a widely cultivated indica hybrid.

Yayou 2 showed a grain yield potential of 12 t/ha, 21 t/ha of biomass (13% higher than that of the check), and a harvest index

of 0.5, which was 6.4% higher than that of the check. Its LAI increased at a rate of 10.2% per day in the earlier growth stages, which was faster than that of the check, and decreased at 2.0% per day in the later stages, which was slower than that of the check. Its maximum LAI was 1.1 and its LAD 25.5%—both higher than those of the check. Yayou 2 had a leaf photosynthetic rate 14.8% higher than the check and a daily bio-mass accumulation of 17.1% more (Table 2).

The leaves of Yayou 2 were droopy during the early growth stage but later became erect, resulting in a lower light extinction coefficient and a higher light transmission in the later stages. Compared with the check, Yayou 2 had a higher translocation coefficient of stored substances in the sheath, leaf, and stem; a higher relative growth rate and net assimilation rate in the earlier stages; and a longer active period for the three top leaves. ■

assessing variation in chemical composition among cultivars and populations of land races. Scientists have also established an association between electrophoretic components and quality characters in cereals.

Glutelin is the major seed storage protein of rice, contributing 80% of the total endosperm protein. We examined the glutelin banding pattern in 72 japonica and indica rices using the sodium dodecyl sulfate PAGE technique. Three were japonica varieties (Jinbu 4, Vailoninano, and Stagaree E) and 69 were indica varieties, classified as nonscented (23), scented (13), glutinous (9), semiglutinous (9), and deepwater (15).

The different indica varieties showed a similar banding pattern for the major bands. The only exception was the scented variety Kosturi. We observed it to have one mobility variant 6s ($R_f = 0.67$) for band 6, which contributed to a higher molecular weight than the corresponding band in other varieties ($R_f = 0.72$). Differences for some minor bands were noticed among subgroups of indica varieties.

Similarly, variation for glutelin subunits was not found within japonica varieties. However, indica and japonica varieties showed variation for the major band 6. The japonica varieties also had a mobility variant 6s ($R_f = 0.67$) similar to that of Kosturi.

These findings show that glutelin components in rice are conserved, unlike prolamines of wheat and barley. The similarity between indica variety Kosturi and japonica varieties for the slow migrating band 6s indicates the probability of these being distantly related. A detailed study is needed to conclude whether the presence or absence of minor bands in different rice groups has something to do with varietal characteristics. ■

Stress tolerance—drought

Leaf rolling and desiccation tolerance in relation to rooting depth and leaf area in rice

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Greater rooting depth is associated with drought tolerance in a rice variety. However, more water is lost from plants with a higher leaf area. A balance between rooting depth and leaf area is perhaps important. This study was done to understand the relative importance of these two traits in leaf rolling and desiccation tolerance.

Different rooting depths were created by placing perforated polyethylene sheets at 5, 10, and 15 cm in the soil. One treatment with no polyethylene sheet was used as the control. Fertilizer at 20-40-60 kg NPK/ha was applied before IR5 was dry

Grain quality

Glutelin banding pattern in rice assessed

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The high stability of the seed protein profile and its additive nature make seed protein electrophoresis a powerful tool in elucidating the origin and evolution of cultivated plants. The electrophoregram obtained by polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) of storage proteins is used mostly for